

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

A STUDY ON THE BACTERIAL VAGINOSIS IN THE DURATION OF PREGNANCY

¹Dr Najam Ul Saqib Malik, ²Dr Muhammad Jalal, ¹Dr Muhammad Usama

¹House officer, Mayo Hospital Lahore

²Medical Officer, Lady Reading Hospital, Peshawar.

Article Received: April 2019

Accepted: May 2019

Published: June 2019

Abstract:

Objective: BV (Bacterial Vaginosis) is one of the important reasons of the discharge from vagina in females. The increase in the preterm labor, miscarriage & PROM (Premature Rupture of Membrane) are very high in the period of pregnancies due to the impact of BV. This research work was carried out to find out the occurrence of BV and to determine its association with miscarriage, preterm pain of labor, IUFD (Intra-uterine fetal death & PROM).

Methodology: This was a chronological cohort research work carried out in 2018. There were one hundred and thirty-six females who were confirm cases of the BV identified before the 20th week of the pregnancy period and total three hundred and ninety-seven females with pregnancy with no BV were the part of non-exposure group. Then, the determination of the association between preterm labor pains, miscarriage, IUFD & PROM with the BV in the duration of pregnancy carried out. SPSS V.11 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information. Chi square test was in use for the comparison of various comparisons and the implementation of the Fisher-exact test & Yates correction carried out implemented whenever necessary. P value of less than 0.050 was significant.

Results: The prevalence of miscarriages, IUFD, preterm labor pain & PROM were 1.30%, 0.90%, 3.60%, 1.30% correspondingly. We found no statistical association between BV & abortion but their association was strong between BV & IUFD, preterm labor pain & PROM.

Conclusion: The results of this research work conclude that the rate of occurrence of IUFD, preterm labor pain & PROM were very high in the females suffering from BV in comparison to the females having no BV.

KEY WORDS: Abortion, Pregnancy, Abnormalities, Preterm, Statistical, Prevalence, Miscarriage, Cohort, Gestational.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Najam Ul Saqib Malik,**

House officer, Mayo Hospital Lahore

QR code

Please cite this article in press Najam Ul Saqib Malik et al., A Study On The Bacterial Vaginosis In The Duration Of Pregnancy., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(06).

INTRODUCTION:

BV is very frequent reason behind discharge from vagina in females [1]. There is rate of occurrence from 10.0% to 31.0% in various research works [2-8]. BV is the cause of many gestational abnormalities like miscarriage, preterm labor pain, premature rupture of membrane & chorioamnionitis [1-9]. It is evident that the danger of preterm births in the females with pregnancy suffering from BV prior to the 16th week of pregnancy period was 1.40 & 6.90 times greater than in the females with pregnancy who did not have this complication [4-8]. This observation states that it is necessary to treat the abnormality before 16th week which is depending upon the mechanism of BV in the abnormality of preterm delivery [10].

The occurrence of the BV in the duration of pregnancy and its association with the preterm labor is different for various populations [11]. The occurrence also depends upon the medical setting, features of socio-demographic aspects, identification standard, duration of pregnancy period and many other factors [12]. There is very deficiency of the information about the impacts of BV on the process of pregnancy in the city of Lahore. The findings of this research work will help the decisions makers of the health care authorities to formulate and implementation of screening & strategies for treatment against BV in the period pregnancy. It elaborated the vitality of this research work.

METHODOLOGY:

This was a chronological cohort research work carried out Mayo Hospital Lahore in the year of 2018. There were total seven hundred and seventy-seven registered females with pregnancy before the 20th week of the pregnancy period. Exposure group contained one hundred and thirty-six females suffering from BV identified before 20th week of pregnancy and three hundred and ninety-seven females with pregnancy without having BV were the participants of non-exposure group. The pregnant females with a past history of abortion, preterm labor pain, multi-fetal pregnancy, past history of various clinical abnormalities in the pregnancies and patients having less than eighteen year of age or more than forty year of age were not the part of this research work. We also interrogated the pregnancy outcomes in the same labor ward of the same hospital.

The analysis of the collected information carried out with the utilization of the SPSS V.11. We used Chi square test for the comparison of different variables & Fisher-exact test/Yates correction methods were in use whenever suitable. The P value of less than 0.050 was the significant.

RESULTS:

In this research work, the occurrence of the BV in the females with pregnancy was 17.50%. There was not much disparity between age groups, profession & birth order in the exposure & non-exposure groups (Table-1).

Table-I: Characteristics of the Pregnant Women According to Bacterial Vaginosis (B.V) Status

Characteristics		B.V positive		B.V Negative		Significance
		No	Percent	No	Percent	
Pregnancy	First	93.0	35.50	169.0	64.50	NS
	Second	36.0	25.50	105.0	74.40	
	>3rd	34.0	34.30	65.0	65.60	
Age Group	<30	124.0	32.70	255.0	67.30	NS
	>30	39.0	32.00	83.0	68.00	
Education	Primary	45.0	30.00	150.0	70.00	NS
	Intermediate	98.0	34.70	184.0	65.20	
	College	18.0	27.70	47.0	72.30	

B.V: Bacterial Vaginosis

The rate of occurrence of abortion, intra-uterine fetal death, preterm labor pain & premature rupture of membrane was 1.3%, 0.90%, 3.60%, 1.30% correspondingly. We were unable to find any statistical association between the occurrence of BV & abortion but the association between BV & IUFD, preterm labor pain & PROM (Table-2) was much significant. The associated danger of the intra-uterine fatal death, preterm labor death & premature rupture of membrane for the pregnant females found positive with bacterial vaginosis were 11.680 (P value of less than 0.0005), 6.320 (P of less than 0.0001) & 25.710 (P value of less than 0.0001) correspondingly.

Table-II: Outcome of Pregnancy Based on Bacterial Vaginosis Status

Outcome		B. V Positive		B. V Negative		Relative risk(95% CI)		Significance
		No	Percent	No	Percent	Value	Range	
Abortion	Yes	4.0	2.90	132.0	97.10	3.890	(0.880 - 17.170)	NS
	No	3.0	0.80	394.0	99.20			
IUFD	Yes	4.0	2.90	132.0	97.10	11/68	(1.320 - 103.570)	<0.0005
	No	1.0	0.30	396.0	99.70			
Preterm labor	Yes	13.0	9.60	123.0	90.40	6.320	(2.240 - 16.310)	<0.0001
	No	6.0	1.50	391.0	98.50			
PROM	Yes	6.0	4.40	130.0	95.60	25.710	(3.290 - 20.070)	<0.0001
	No	1.0	0.30	396.0	99.70			

B.V: Bacterial V vaginosis IUFD: Intra uterine fetal death PROM: Premature rupture of membrane

DISCUSSION:

The range of the occurrence of BV was from 6.80% to 28.0% in the research works conducted in various hospitals in various countries of the world [13, 2, 11, 14, 16], but there was not much data about this complication in our population [13]. The rate of occurrence of BV, miscarriage, intra-uterine fetal death, preterm labor pain and premature rupture of membrane in this research work were 17.50%, 1.30%, 0.90%, 3.60% & 1.30% correspondingly. There was not association between BV & abortion but high rate of occurrence of intra-uterine fatal deaths, preterm labor pain & premature rupture of membrane was available in the females having infection of BV. There is suggestion that danger of the preterm labor pain was very high in the pregnancies having complications due to BV [17].

In his research work, Kalinkaj reported the rate of occurrence of preterm labor was 15.70% in comparison with 9.10% among females who did not have BV and the findings concluded that that in time identification of the BV and treatment of this complication has the ability to reduce the preterm labor [2]. In one research work conducted in Paris, preterm labor in the females suffering from the BV was about 25.0% in comparison with the 10.60% in other females [11]. In the research work of Hiller, preterm labor & the low weight at the tie of birth were very common in females having the complication of BV [14]. In the research work of Benedetto, there was significant association of the BV with the premature rupture of membrane & preterm delivery but it has no association with the intra-uterine fetal death [15].

Ralph in his research work, measured the risk of abortion in females suffering from BV as about 32.10% in comparison with the 18.50% in the females with no BV [16]. In accordance with one other research work, among females suffering from BV, the danger of preterm labor was very high and it was the suggestion that anti-bacterial treatment could reduce the danger of preterm labor [18]. In accordance with this research work, the treatment of the BV in pregnant females might cause a reduction in the rates of miscarriage, premature rupture of membranes, intra-uterine fetal death & preterm labor. Ugwumdau in his research work displayed that screening & treatment of the BV without symptoms in 1st month of the 2nd trimester can reduce the rate of occurrence of preterm labor in the females with pregnancy [19] & some other research works illustrated the same results [20] but Goffeng in his research work was not able to find any association between BV & preterm labor [3] & on the basis of one other research work in Toronto, the treatment of BV did not reduce the danger of preterm labor & did not have any impact on the outcome of the pregnancy [21]. Oakeshott discovered that BV is not a positive prognostication of abortions before the 16th week of the pregnancy duration [22]. Liversedge in his research work concluded no important disparity in abortions in the result of BV, Ralph discovered the important association in the duration of 1st three months of pregnancy [20, 23].

CONCLUSION:

In accordance with the results of this research work, the rates of intra-uterine fetal death, preterm labor pain & premature rupture were very high in the pregnant females who were suffering from BV in comparison with the females who were not suffering from BV.

This is very important for the gynecologist & midwives to screen the pregnant females prior to the 20th week of the pregnancy period for bacterial vaginosis and to treat this issue to reduce the danger of the intra-uterine fetal death and premature rupture of membrane.

REFERENCES:

1. Kurki T, Sivonen A, Renkonen O, Savia E, Ylikorkala O. Bacterial vaginosis in early pregnancy and pregnancy outcome. *Obstet Gynaecol* 1992; 80:173-7.
2. Riduan JM, Hillier SL, Utomo B, Wiknjastro G, Linnan M, Kandun N. Bacterial vaginosis and prematurity in Indonesia: association in early and late pregnancy. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1993; 169:175-8.
3. Hay PE, Lamont RF, Taylor-Robinson D, Morgan DJ, Ison C, Pearson J. Abnormal bacterial colonisation of the genital tract and subsequent pre-term delivery and late miscarriage. *BMJ* 1994; 308:295-8.
4. McGregor JA, French JJ, Parker R, Draper D, Patterson E, Jones W, et al. Prevention of premature birth by screening and treatment for common genital tract infections: results of a prospective controlled evaluation. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1995; 173:157-67.
5. Hillier SL, Nugent RP, Eschenbach DA, Krohn MA, Gibbs RS, Martin DH, et al. Association between bacterial vaginosis and preterm delivery of a low-birth-weight infant. *N Engl J Med* 1995; 333:1737-42.
6. Leitich H, Bodner-Adler B, Brunbauer M, Kaider A, Egarter C, Husslein P. Bacterial vaginosis as a risk factor for preterm delivery: A meta-analysis. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 2003; 189:139-147.
7. Gary Cunningham, Kenneth J. Leveno, Steven L. Bloom, John C. Hauth, Larry C. Gilstrap, Katharine D. Wenstrom. *William's Manual of Obstetrics*, United States, McGraw-Hill, 2007, p: 1021-50.
8. Guise JM, Mahon SM, Aickin M, Helfand M, Peipert JF, Westhoff C. Screening for bacterial vaginosis in pregnancy. *Am J Prev Med* 2001; 20:62-72.
9. Hauth JC, Goldenberg RL, Andrews WW, DuBard MB, Copper RL. Reduced incidence of preterm delivery with metronidazole and erythromycin in women with bacterial vaginosis. *N Engl J Med* 1995; 333:1732-6.
10. Kalinka J, Ludański T, Hanke W, Krzemiński Z, Wasiela M. The evaluation of prevalence and the impact of pathological microflora of the lower genital tract among women at early pregnancy on the risk of preterm delivery. *Med Dosw Mikrobiol* 2003; 55:277-84.
11. Oakeshott P, Hay P, Hay S, Steinke F, Rink E, Kerry S. Association between bacterial vaginosis or chlamydial infection and miscarriage before 16 weeks' gestation: prospective community based cohort study. *BMJ* 2002; 325:1334.
12. Goffinet F, Maillard F, Mihoubi N, Kayem G, Papiernik E, Cabrol D, Paul G. Bacterial vaginosis: prevalence and predictive value for premature delivery and neonatal infection in women with preterm labour and intact membranes. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol* 2003; 108:146-51
13. Goffeng AR, Holst E, Milsom I, Lindstedt G, Lundberg PA, Andersch B. Fetal fibronectin and microorganisms in vaginal fluid of women with complicated pregnancies. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand* 1997; 76:521-7.
14. Trabert B, Misra DP. Risk factors for bacterial vaginosis during pregnancy among African American women. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 2007; 197:477-8. Sholeh Shahgeibi et al.
15. U.S. Preventive Services Task Force. Screening for Bacterial Vaginosis in Pregnancy to Prevent Preterm Delivery: U.S. Preventive Services Task Force Recommendation Statement. *Ann Intern Med* 2008; 148:214-219
16. Oakeshott- Liversedge N, Turner A, Horner PJ, Keay S, Jenkins J, Hull M. The influence of bacterial vaginosis on in-vitro fertilisation and embryo implanta-tion during assisted reproduction treatment. *Hum Reprod* 1999; 14:2411-5.
17. Hillier SL, Nugent RP, Eschenbach DA, Krohn MA, Gibbs RS, Martin DH, et al. Association between bacterial vaginosis and preterm delivery of a low-birth-weight infant. The Vaginal Infections and Prematurity Study Group. *N Engl J Med* 1995; 333:1737-42
18. Benedetto C, Tibaldi C, Marozio L, Marini S, Masuelli G, Pelissetto S, et al. Cervicovaginal infections during pregnancy: epidemiological and microbiological aspects. *J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med* 2004; 2:9-12.
19. Ralph SG, Rutherford AJ, Wilson JD. Influence of bacterial vaginosis on conception and miscarriage in the first trimester: cohort study. *BMJ* 1999; 319:220-3.
20. Hay P, Lamont R, Taylor-Robinson D, Morgan D, Ison C, Pearson J. Abnormal bacterial colonisation of the genital tract and subsequent pre-term delivery and late miscarriage. *BMJ* 1994; 308:295-8.

21. French JI, McGregor JA, Draper D, Parker R, McFee J. Gestational bleeding, bacterial vaginosis, and common reproductive tract infections: risk for preterm birth and benefit of treatment. *Obstet Gynecol* 1999; 93:715-24.
22. Ugwumadu A, Manyonda I, Reid F, Hay P. Effect of early oral clindamycin on late miscarriage and preterm delivery in asymptomatic women with abnormal vaginal flora and bacterial vaginosis: a randomised controlled trial. *Lancet* 2003; 361:983-8.
23. Kiss H, Petricevic L, Husslein P. Prospective randomized controlled trial of an infection screening program to reduce the rate of preterm delivery. *BMJ* 2004; 329:374.